

Running title: Closing yield gaps through increased efficiency of chickpea production in Ethiopia

Estimating the potential to close yield gaps through increased efficiency of chickpea production in Ethiopia

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1 **Estimating the potential to close yield gaps through** 2 **increased efficiency of chickpea production in Ethiopia**

3 **Abstract**

4 Improved cultivars and agronomic practices have significantly increased chickpea production in
5 Ethiopia in recent decades. Enhanced availability of chickpeas in Ethiopia, therefore, contributes to
6 food, nutrition, and income security of the country. However, we know relatively little about the
7 extent to which farmers have harnessed the full potential of these improved technologies. In this
8 paper, we compare the technical efficiencies and technological gap ratios of chickpea farming in three
9 major chickpea-producing areas of Ethiopia using a two-step meta frontier model. Based on regionally
10 representative data from 681 chickpea-growing farm households in the three regions, we show
11 regional differences in the technical efficiencies, technological gap ratios, and meta technical
12 efficiencies (MTEs). We examined the drivers of these different production levels and identified ways
13 to increase chickpea production while minimizing yield gaps. Improving technical efficiency through
14 improving farmers' access to improved seed, offering farmers need-based and gender-responsive
15 extension support, encouraging their participation in technology development programs, and appropriate
16 rainwater management would all contribute to harnessing the full potential of improved chickpea cultivars
17 in Ethiopia.

18 **Keywords:** Chickpea production, technical efficiency, stochastic meta-frontier, technology gap, yield
19 gap, potential production loss, Ethiopia

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23 **1. Introduction**

24 After decades of slow progress, several countries in Africa are on the path to economic
25 transformation. In Ethiopia, this transformation is partially driven by agricultural development
26 and has led to a substantial reduction of poverty and food insecurity in rural areas (Dercon et al.
27 2009; World Bank 2020). Despite the contribution of agriculture to economic progress, yield
28 gaps in African farming remain high (Affholder et al. 2013; van Ittersum et al. 2016). The yield
29 gaps are generally defined as the difference between the potential yield achievable on a research
30 station and the actual yield farmers obtain for a given biophysical environment (van Ittersum and
31 Rabbinge 1997). However, in this study, we consider the yield gap for a particular farm
32 household as the difference between its crop yield and the yield achieved by the most efficient
33 farmer for the given level of inputs (Mueller et al., 2012; Titonell and Giller, 2013). In many
34 African countries, the yield gaps in staple crops reduce the amount of foods that reach domestic
35 markets, contribute to food shortages, and increase the dependency on food imports and aid
36 (Abate et al. 2015). Though farming is just one contributor to the economic transformation in
37 Africa, if yield gaps could be reduced, the economic footprint of agriculture in Africa would be
38 substantial.

39
40 Available farm efficiency analyses suggest important insights into the potential of farms to close
41 yield gaps and improve agricultural productivity. Agricultural productivity is a function of the
42 output produced with a given quantity of inputs. Estimating farm efficiency has been the subject
43 of considerable interest to researchers in recent decades. Several efficiency studies in Africa
44 were used to raise policy debates on the performance of the agricultural sector (Abro et al. 2014;
45 Akamin et al. 2017; Belete 2020). However, a number of studies examining efficiency in crop

46 production in developing countries (Coelli and Battese 1996; Bravo-Ureta et al. 2007; Majumder
47 et al. 2016) have shown mixed and inconsistent results across different modelling approaches
48 and agro-ecological conditions. These studies for specific crops typically used a nonparametric
49 approach (Assefa 2020; Geta et al. 2013; Mussa et al. 2012; Tiruneh and Geta 2016), which has
50 limitations in terms of statistical robustness. Yet, statistical robustness is key for understanding
51 the technical efficiency¹ (TE) of different farms is an essential step towards harnessing the full
52 potential of improved crop cultivars.

53

54 Despite commercial interests, the farmers growing grain legumes also suffer from yield gaps.
55 Yet, grain legumes have significant potential to improve household food security, nutrition, and
56 to commercialize agriculture and contribute to economic transformation (Gwata 2010). Chickpea
57 (*Cicer arietinum*), for example, is a multipurpose legume with numerous benefits to farmers.
58 Chickpea is an essential source of protein and micronutrients with the potential to reduce
59 malnutrition (Jukanti et al. 2012). It also contributes to household incomes, food security, and
60 exports and a source of foreign exchange (Verkaart et al. 2017). Enhanced chickpea production
61 can create opportunities for local value-added processing, stimulate domestic demand, provide
62 off-farm employment and enrich diets for consumers (Getachew 2019). Understanding the yield
63 gaps and efficiency of chickpea production is important to develop policy measures that help
64 increase chickpea production, productivity and farm profitability sustainably.

65

¹ Technical efficiency is the effectiveness with which a given set of inputs is used to produce an output. A farm is said to be technically efficient if the farm is producing the maximum output from the given quantity of inputs, such as labour, capital, and technology.

66 In Africa, Ethiopia offers an interesting case to study chickpeas. Ethiopia is the sixth-largest
67 producer of chickpea globally and the largest in Africa (Rawal and Navarro 2019). Chickpea is
68 Ethiopia's third most important export legume after faba bean and haricot bean, generating a
69 revenue of about US\$61 million annually (CSA 2019). As a result, chickpea is one of the main
70 pulse crops in the country in terms of cropped area, total production, and direct human
71 consumption. It is cultivated by more than 900,000 households on an estimated 239,786 ha of
72 land, and in 2018 total production reached to 459,173 t, with an average grain yield of 2.25 t ha⁻¹
73 for the smaller *desi* type and 1.68 t ha⁻¹ for the lighter-coloured *Kabuli* type (CSA 2019).
74 The chickpea area, production, and productivity in Ethiopia have continuously increased in the
75 past two decades (Fig. 1). These trends underline the importance of the crop in the country and
76 demonstrate the importance of the productivity-enhancing interventions being adopted by
77 farmers. Food Agriculture Organization (FAO) data for the past 18 years (2000–2018) showed
78 that chickpea area, production, and productivity has increased in Ethiopia by 30.5%, 213.2%,
79 and 140.0%, respectively. The higher rate of increment in productivity compared to the increase
80 in the area shows that the production increase is mostly driven by productivity improvement.

81 **Figure 1 about here**

82 Legume intensification programs such as the CGIAR 'Tropical Legumes' project improved
83 chickpea yields (Ojiewo et al. 2019) in Ethiopia. The adoption of improved chickpea cultivars of
84 both *desi* and *Kabuli* types by Ethiopian farmers has contributed substantially to poverty
85 reduction by improving food security and household income (Verkaart et al. 2017 & 2019).
86 Profitable expansion of chickpea as a second crop using residual moisture has also contributed to
87 sustainable intensification of cropping systems (Ojiewo et al. 2019).

88

89 While participatory varietal trials, on-farm demonstrations, and seeds in small packs at scale and
90 capacity building programs contributed to intensifying chickpea production in Ethiopia (Ojiewo
91 et al. 2019), there are interregional and intra-regional differences due to differences in the agro-
92 ecologies, production conditions and socio-economic contexts. Chickpea is currently cultivated
93 in four regions of Ethiopia (Amhara, Oromia, SNNP, and Tigray). Amhara and Oromia together
94 account for 93% of total production, while SNNP and Tigray contribute only 3.5% and 3%,
95 respectively. This difference between the regions offers sufficient heterogeneity to study the
96 potential regional differences in TE and its effect on production achieved at a given level of
97 inputs. Knowledge of the performance of chickpea production and distribution of TE across
98 farms in different regions will help identify the extent of preventable yield gaps with the current
99 level of inputs. Understanding how different regions in Ethiopia are adopting chickpea
100 production technologies will help identify new entry points for policy and agricultural extension
101 services offered to the farmers.

102 With this perspective, we assess the technical efficiency and technological gaps in chickpea
103 production within and across different regions of Ethiopia using the stochastic meta-frontier
104 model proposed by Huang et al. (2014). We contribute to the yield gap literature by estimating
105 intra-regional and inter-regional technical efficiency, Technological Gap Ratios² (TGRs), and
106 potential chickpea production losses in Ethiopia resulting from technical inefficiency. First, we
107 identify the TE and TGRs of chickpea production for Amhara, Oromia, and SNNP. Second, we
108 determine the drivers of chickpea production and its efficiency in these regions; third, to estimate
109 the potential for enhancing chickpea production by improving the TE. The remainder of this
110 paper is organized as follows. Section 2 outlines the theoretical model and methodology

² The ratio of a particular farm's production frontier to the meta-frontier is defined as the technology gap ratio (Huang, 2014).

111 underpinning our analysis. section 3 presents the results of empirical estimations, which are
112 discussed in section 4. Section 5 offers our conclusions and implications for agricultural policy
113 in Ethiopia.

114

115 **2. Methodology**

116

117 **2.1 Study area and data**

118 For this study covering three major chickpea growing regions (Amhara, Oromia, and SNNP) of Ethiopia,
119 we utilized data collected under the CGIAR-led Tropical Legume (TL) project for 2017 and 2018. Under
120 the TL project, 681 regionally-representative and randomly-selected chickpea-producing farm households
121 were surveyed from the three regions. The survey data points for chickpea-cultivating farm households
122 are shown in Fig. 2.

123 **Figure 2 about here**

124

125 In the sampled farm households, Kabuli cultivars dominated the chickpea area. About 66% of the
126 area was under Kabuli chickpea cultivars, and the remaining 34% under Desi cultivars. Among the
127 improved Kabuli varieties, Arerti was the most popular (planted in about 52% of the total chickpea area)
128 followed by Habru and Shasho. Dubie was the most popular improved Desi variety, followed by Natoli
129 and Marive (Table 1).

130 **Table 1 about here**

131 **2.1.1 Main input and output variables**

132 The Cobb-Douglas model used in our analysis consists of one output variable and six input variables.
133 Output included chickpea production (kg grain) per farm household. The Cobb-Douglas production
134 function in the empirical model (see equation 7 below) is specified using six input variables: as the area of

135 cultivated land (kert³) used for chickpea crop (both owned and net leased in); the total amount of seed
136 (kg) used; the total number of labor days used for chickpea production, including hired labor and family
137 labor; the number of oxen used for ploughing; NPS⁴ fertilizer used (kg) and the total amount of pesticides
138 (liter) used. All the inputs are not always used by all the farm households while producing a crop. Thus
139 there were zero values also for some of the inputs except land, seed, and human labor in our dataset. ,
140 The appropriate parameter of Cobb-Douglas production functions can be estimated unbiasedly by using a
141 dummy variable associated with such zero observations (Battese 1997). Accordingly, following Battese
142 et al. (1996), Battese (1997), O'Donnell et al. (2008), and Huang et al. (2014), we used three dummy
143 variables: D1, D2, and D3 for NPS use, pesticide use, and oxen use respectively; the value for D1, D2 and
144 D3 is 1 when NPS, pesticide, and oxen are used in production and 0 if not ⁵.

145

146 **2.1.2 Environmental variables**

147 A review of existing literature and focus group discussions with farmers and other stakeholders were
148 conducted to identify the key variables that potentially influence the efficiency of chickpea production in
149 Ethiopia. Our empirical analysis was executed in a two-step procedure, in which several environmental
150 variables were considered in the formulation of group-specific and industry-specific frontiers to analyze
151 the effects of environmental factors on production efficiency and the technology gap. The environmental
152 variables in this analysis are those which indirectly influence the efficiency of chickpea production and
153 were divided into household-specific and region-specific variables. The former variables were used in the
154 first-step estimation of the group frontiers set out in Equation (4), which influence farm-specific technical
155 efficiency. A farm is said to be technically most efficient if the farm is producing the maximum output
156 from the given quantity of inputs, such as land, labour, capital, and technology. The latter types of

³ 4 kert = 1 hectare (ha)

⁴ NPS is a new compound fertilizer recently used in Ethiopia containing nitrogen, phosphorous and Sulphur with the ratio of 19% N, 38% P₂O₅ and 7% S.

⁵ Technically, NPS and pesticide use data are not used directly in the model; more specifically, they were used in the form of $\ln(\max(input_i, 1 - D_i))$ where i is the particular input.

157 variables were utilized in the second-step estimation of the meta-frontier in Equation (5), which
158 characterizes the environment affecting the choice of production technologies.

159 We considered the following six farm household-specific environmental variables: - the
160 experience of growing chickpea, the proportion of women participating in agricultural activity, the
161 proportion of chickpea area under improved varieties, the average age of household members
162 participating in farm production, average numbers of years of education of members of the household and
163 participation in the technology transfer program under the TL project. We also considered the following
164 two industry/region-specific environmental variables: the coefficient of variation (CV) of rainfall
165 during 2007-2018 and the farm household's distance from the market, which indicates the access to input
166 and output markets. Table 2 summarizes the sample statistics for the three study regions, including the
167 output, inputs, and environmental variables.

168 **Table 2 about here**

169

170 **2.2 Analytical framework**

171 We used a robust stochastic meta-frontier model for technical efficiency analysis for this paper. Battese
172 and Coelli (1995) developed a two-stage inefficiency effect model. In the first stage, the farm-specific
173 technical efficiency estimates are estimated using the production function. In the second stage, a
174 regression approach is adopted to identify the factors that influence efficiency differentials. Meta frontier
175 analysis was first introduced by Hayami (1969) and Hayami and Ruttan (1970; 1971). Battese et al.
176 (2004) and O'Donnell et al. (2008) further developed the modern meta-frontier production function
177 model. Their model was estimated in two steps: The stochastic frontier (SF) regression which is used in
178 the first step to estimate the group-specific frontier combined with the mathematical programming
179 techniques. In the second step, the meta-frontier is estimated. However, there were no statistical
180 properties of the resulting meta-frontier estimation in the second step due to linear (or quadratic)

181 programming algebraic calculation. Further, this method did not account for potentially different
 182 production environments facing farms that can be incorporated into the estimation and failed to isolate
 183 idiosyncratic shocks (Huang et al. 2014). To overcome these weaknesses, Huang et al. (2014) proposed a
 184 new two-step SF approach to estimate the group-specific frontiers and the meta-frontier, respectively, and
 185 decompose the efficiency scores of various groups' into TE and technology gaps. The main difference
 186 between the two-step SF approach and that of Battese et al. (2004) and O'Donnell et al. (2008) is that the
 187 former's second-step estimation of the meta-frontier is based on the SF framework providing statistical
 188 properties of the estimates, rather than on a mathematical programming technique.

189 A general conventional stochastic production frontier model with j^{th} production region and the
 190 i^{th} decision-making unit (DMU) or a firm in the t^{th} period is given by:

$$191 Y_{jit} = f_t^j(X_{jit})e^{V_{jit}-U_{jit}}, j = 1, 2, \dots, J; i = 1, 2, \dots, N_j; t = 1, 2, \dots, T \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

192 Where y_{jit} denotes the output level for farm i in the j^{th} region in the t^{th} time period, X_{jit} is the input
 193 vector, V_{jit} represents the error term and is assumed to be iid as $V_{jit} \sim N(0, \sigma_v^{j2})$. U_{jit} representing
 194 technical inefficiency and is distributed as $U_{jit} \sim N^+(\mu^j(Z_{jit}), \sigma_u^{j2}(Z_{jit}))$, i.e. truncated from below at
 195 zero and with the mode at $\mu^j(Z_{jit})$, where Z_{jit} s are some exogenous variables. A firm's technical
 196 efficiency (TE) in production is then defined as:

$$197 TE_{it}^j = \frac{Y_{jit}}{f_t^j(X_{jit})e^{V_{jit}}} = e^{-U_{jit}} \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

198 To estimate the stochastic meta-frontier function that envelops all the frontiers of the k regions,
 199 we use the approach developed by Huang et al (2014). In step 2, therefore, the following SFA was
 200 specified:

$$201 \hat{f}_t^j(X_{jit}) = f_t^M(X_{ijt})e^{-U_{jit}^M}, \quad \forall j, i, t \dots\dots\dots (3)$$

202 where the $\hat{f}_t^j(X_{jit})$ are the predictions from the group frontiers from step 1 in (1).

203 As discussed in detail in Huang et al., (2014), at a given input level X_{ijt} , the observed

204 output Y_{jit} of the i^{th} farm relative to the meta-frontier consists of three components, that is,

205
$$\frac{Y_{jit}}{f_t^M(X_{jit})} = TGR_{it}^j \times TE_{it}^j \times e^{V_{jit}}$$
, where $TGR_{it}^j = \frac{f_t^j(X_{jit})}{\hat{f}_t^M(X_{jit})}$ is the technology gap ratio, $TE_{it}^j =$

206
$$\frac{f_t^j(X_{jit})e^{-U_{jit}}}{f_t^j(X_{jit})} = e^{-U_{jit}}$$
 is the firm's technical efficiency, and $\frac{Y_{jit}}{f_t^M(X_{ijt})e^{-U_{jit}^M}} = e^{V_{jit}}$ is the random noise

207 component.

208 Then, the two-step approach to estimate the meta-frontier as proposed by Huang et al., (2014) consists of

209 two SFA regressions:

210
$$\ln Y_{jit} = \ln f_t^j(X_{ijt}) + V_{jit} - U_{jit}, i = 1, 2, \dots, N_j; t = 1, 2, \dots, T \dots \dots \dots (4)$$

211
$$\ln \hat{f}_t^j(X_{jit}) = f_t^M(X_{ijt}) + V_{jit}^M - U_{jit}^M, \forall j, i, t = 1, 2, \dots, J \dots \dots \dots (5)$$

212 Where $\ln \hat{f}_t^j(X_{jit})$ is the estimates of the group-specific frontier from the first step in (4). Since the

213 estimates $\ln \hat{f}_t^j(X_{jit})$ are group-specific, the regression (4) is estimated J times, one for each group (j =

214 1, 2, ..., J). These estimates from all J groups are then pooled to estimate (5).

215 The group-specific frontier to be larger than or equal to the meta-frontier, i.e. $\hat{f}_t^j(X_{jit}) \geq f_t^M(X_{ijt})$, due

216 to the error of estimating $f_t^j(X_{ijt})$. However, the meta-frontier should be larger than or equal to the

217 group-specific frontier, $f_t^j(X_{ijt}) \leq f_t^M(X_{ijt})$. The estimated technology gap ratio (TGR) must always be

218 less than or equal to unity,

219
$$\widehat{TGR}_{it}^j = \hat{E} \left(e^{-U_{jit}^M} \mid \hat{\varepsilon}_{jit}^M \right) \leq 1 \dots \dots \dots (6)$$

220 Where $\hat{\varepsilon}_{jit}^M = \ln \hat{f}_t^j(X_{jit}) - \ln f_t^M(X_{ijt})$ are the estimated composite residuals of (5). The meta technical

221 efficiency (MTE) of the i^{th} farm to the meta-frontier is equal to the product of the estimate of the TGR in

222 Equation (6) and the individual farm's estimated TE in Equation (2), that is,

246 $TE_i = \frac{Y_i}{Y_i^*}$ (8)

247 Where TE_i is the technical efficiency of the i^{th} farm household for chickpea production; Y_i^* is the
 248 frontier/potential output of chickpea for the i^{th} farm household if it is perfectly technically efficient at the
 249 current level of inputs, and Y_i is the actual/observed output of the i^{th} farm household.

250 Then, solving for Y_i^* the potential chickpea production of each household is represented as:

251 $Y_i^* = \frac{Y_i}{TE_i}$ (9)

252 Thus the potential loss of chickpea production due to technical inefficiency would be

253 $YG = Y_i^* - Y_i$ (10)

254

255 **3. Results**

256 Although Ethiopia has seen significant advances in chickpea production and area planted in the past two
 257 decades (Fig. 2), our data show that the grain yields have significantly varied within and across the three
 258 study regions (Table 3). *Oromia* had the highest average yield (1879 kg ha⁻¹) with the highest variation
 259 (854.96 kg ha⁻¹), followed by the Amhara (1502 kg ha⁻¹ with the variation of 702.02 kg ha⁻¹) and SNNP
 260 (1471 kg ha⁻¹ with the variation of 552.26 kg ha⁻¹). Overall average yield was 1704.11 kg ha⁻¹ with the
 261 variation of 764.88 kg ha⁻¹.

262 **Figure 2 about here**

263 **Table 3 about here**

264

265 To understand whether all three regions were using the same level of technology and whether all
 266 chickpea production points were part of a single production frontier, we applied the likelihood ratio (LR)

267 test⁶ to the null hypothesis that the production frontiers were the same for the three regions. The value of
268 the restricted log-likelihood function under the null hypothesis was 227.3181, while the unrestricted value
269 was -27.5529, which is the sum of the three log-likelihood function values reported in Table 4. The
270 degree of freedom for the chi-square distribution was 38. The likelihood ratio statistic estimated was
271 509.7420, which is twice the difference between the unrestricted and restricted log-likelihood function
272 values. Thus, the hypothesis that production frontiers are the same for the three regions is decisively
273 rejected at the 0.1% level⁷. In other words, the three regions are operating under heterogeneous levels of
274 technology use⁸. The existence of potential production technology gaps among the three regions justifies
275 the estimation of the meta-frontier production function for analyzing chickpea production in Ethiopia.

276

277 **3.1 Input elasticities**

278 The estimate⁹ for the group-specific chickpea production function in the three study regions, the
279 pooled data model, and the meta-frontier model are presented in Table 4. The frontier model for the
280 pooled data for the three individual regions and the meta frontier exhibited positive input coefficients
281 except for NPS use and D3 (dummy for oxen use), and 80% of the parameter estimates were statistically
282 significant at the 10% level.

283 **Table 4 about here**

⁶ The LR statistic is defined by, $\lambda = -2 \left[\ln \left(\frac{L_{Ho}}{L_{H1}} \right) \right] = -2 [\ln L_{Ho} - \ln L_{H1}]$, where $\ln L_{Ho}$ is the value of the log-likelihood function for the stochastic frontier estimated by pooling the data for all groups under the homoscedastic variance component, and $\ln L_{H1}$ is the sum of the values of the log-likelihood functions for the separate group frontiers (Rao et al. 2004, Battese et al. 2004, O'Donnell et al. 2008) with a chi-square (χ^2) distribution with degrees of freedom $d = \sum_{j=1}^J \dim(\beta^j) - \dim(\beta^M)$, where $\dim(\cdot)$ is the dimension of the parameter. (Huang and Lai 2017).

⁷ The table value of Chi-square (χ^2) distribution with degrees of freedom 38 at 0.1% level is 70.703

⁸ This is a necessary step of the meta-frontier analysis procedure. In the cases when the likelihood ratio test doesn't not show the difference in technology use among the regions, then it is not suggested to use meta-frontier analysis for the study of technical efficiency.

⁹ We used the "frontier" package in R developed by Coelli and Henningsen (2013).

284 The coefficients of SFs for land use in the three regions, the pooled data, and the meta frontier
285 were the largest, positive, and highly significant at the 1% level among other partial production input
286 elasticities. The estimated elasticity of chickpea production for seed use was positively significant in all
287 regions except SNNP where the estimates were positive but not significant, with values ranging from
288 0.0831 to 0.1668. The coefficient of labor use was also positively significant in all regions including
289 pooled data and the meta frontier, with values ranging from 0.0778 to 0.2919. This made it the second
290 most important factor for chickpea production after land use.

291 NPS fertilizer use was negative and non-significant (except the meta-frontier model where it was
292 negatively significant), but the corresponding dummy variable D1 was positive and highly significant
293 (except for SNNP). The coefficients for pesticide use and its corresponding dummy D2 were positive and
294 highly significant suggesting that pesticides and the way farmers apply them have positively influenced
295 chickpea production. This is plausible since many farmers have access to and awareness of the
296 appropriate use of pesticides. The magnitude of the coefficient of pesticide use ranged from 0.0832 to
297 0.2894. The use of oxen for ploughing was positive and significant for all the regions, pooled data, and
298 meta frontier, but its corresponding dummy variable D3 gave mixed and non-significant coefficients
299 except in the Amhara, where it was positive and significant.

300

301 **3.2 Technical Efficiency (TE), Technology Gap Ratio (TGR), and Meta Technical** 302 **Efficiency (MTE)**

303 The Tropical Legumes Project and other legume intensification programs have promoted high yielding
304 (HY) cultivars of chickpea in Ethiopia. The full potential of these cultivars can be realized only by
305 appropriately and efficiently using various production practices and inputs (table 2). Table 5 reports the
306 estimated TE, TGR, and MTE scores for the three study regions. The average group-specific TE score for
307 chickpea crop production was low at 0.5314.

308

309 **Table 5 about here**

310 In Amhara, farmers had the highest average TE score of 0.5678 with a range from 0.2974 to 0.9510,
311 followed by SNNP with an average score of 0.5236 in the range of 0.2072 to 0.9856. Oromia had the
312 lowest average TE score of 0.4936, ranging from 0.15444 to 0.9999 (Table 5). The likelihood ratio test
313 for our model indicates that farmers in the different regions of Ethiopia did not have the same level of
314 technology use. The average TE scores of all three regions were low, ranging from 0.4936 to 0.5678.
315 While the average TE score of all three regions falls within a small range, the distribution of scores across
316 farm households varied a lot¹⁰. Another significant result was that a large proportion of farmers were
317 operating below a reasonable TE score of 0.6 (Fig. 4).

318 **Figure 4 about here**

319 The Stochastic Meta Frontier (SMF) estimate of the mean value of the TGR scores was 0.9665,
320 ranging from 0.9622 to 0.9711, which is very close to 1. A TGR value of 1 is equivalent to a point where
321 the individual regional frontier coincides with the meta-frontier. That indicates a situation when the most
322 efficient farmers in a region is operating at the same level as the most efficient farmer on a global
323 (country) scale. The Amhara region had an average TGR of 0.9711 with a range of 0.8558 to 1 versus an
324 average TGR of 0.9630 for Oromia with a range of 0.8874 to 1 and an average TGR of 0.9622 for SNNP
325 ranging from 0.8672 to 1. The maximum TGR value was 1 for all three regions individually, indicating
326 that some farms in each region were equally technically efficient and produced the maximum output per
327 unit of inputs given the current technology as noted from the meta-frontier (Fig. 4). However, on average,
328 the farmers in Amhara were relatively ahead in adopting the technology, followed by Oromia and SNNP.

¹⁰ Theoretically, TE score could be anywhere between 1 and 0, with the most efficient farm's TE score is close to one. Here the highest TE score is 0.9999, and the lowest is 0.1544. therefore, the variation is very high for individual farm households. However, the average TE score of the three regions is between 0.4936 and 0.5678. It may be noted that TE is not indicating the level of technology use but the efficiency of input use; the low TE score farms might be using different inputs inefficiently.

329 The average MTE score, which considers all regions, was 0.5131, ranging from 0.1541 to 0.9949. The TE
330 and TGR scores, indicate that Amhara’s chickpea production was technically more efficient than Oromia
331 and SNNP.

332 We further verified whether the differences between mean efficiency scores across the three
333 regions were statistically significant. The paired t-test statistics of the null hypothesis indicating that there
334 was no true mean difference were rejected at least at a 10% level of significance for most of the cases.
335 Therefore, we conclude that the various TE scores were not equal across the regions (Table 6).

336 **Table 6 about here**

337

338 **3.3 Determinants of Farm-specific and Region-specific efficiency**

339 Table 4 also summarizes the coefficients for the farm-specific and region-specific environmental
340 variables illustrating the technical inefficiency. An environmental variable that has a negative (positive)
341 coefficient implies that the variable exerts a positive (negative) impact on technical efficiency. We found
342 that farmers’ longer experience of growing chickpea was found to be positively influencing the efficiency
343 of production in the SNNP region but had a negative influence in Oromia. Our results show a positive and
344 significant relationship between technical efficiency and the proportion of women worker participants in
345 chickpea production at the household level. This is reflected in the negative and significant coefficient
346 estimates and a high magnitude for this variable in all the regions as well as in the pooled data (Table 4).
347 We also found that the average age of household members had a negative and significant effect on
348 inefficiency. This result suggests that higher average age would positively influence the efficiency of
349 chickpea production. This may be interpreted in the context that the average age of farmers ranges from
350 33 to 35 years. Plausibly a greater engagement of the households’ older members in chickpea production
351 might have resulted in a positive relationship of age with technical efficiency. The analysis of

352 determinants of technical efficiency as depicted in Table 4 shows that education as formal years of
353 schooling had a significant positive effect on the efficiency of chickpea production.

354 Finally, the coefficients in Table 4 show that the access to technology, information, and capacity
355 building/training of farmers on improved chickpea crop production through participatory technology
356 transfer programs and use of improved seed promoted by the Tropical Legumes (TL) Project played a key
357 role in enhancing the technical efficiency of chickpea production. The results suggest that farmers’
358 participation in technology transfer programs had a strong positive and significant influence on the
359 efficiency of chickpea production for all three study regions individually and for the pooled data.
360 Similarly, a higher proportion of chickpea area under improved varieties also had a strong positive and
361 significant influence on production efficiency for all the regions (except SNNP) and in the pooled data.
362 This finding implies that farmers who participated in the TL project achieved much higher technical
363 efficiency than their counterparts.

364 The coefficient of variation (CV) of rainfall and distance from the market were included as
365 region-specific environmental variables in the model. The CV of rainfall had a significant and positive
366 coefficient and thus had a negative relationship with technical efficiency, which was expected. Higher
367 variability of rainfall, which leads to lower technical efficiency impacting crop production, might be on
368 account of both more prolonged dry spells and extreme high rainfall events resulting in waterlogging.
369 Another variable, distance from the market, was negative but not significant. The distance from the
370 market is a crucial variable and likely to influence the profitability and (dis) incentivize farmers to make
371 investments in technology/inputs for crop production, nevertheless, it was not significant that might be
372 because most of the farmers were operating at a similar distance from the market.

373 **3.4 Potential crop production losses due to inefficiency**

374 We estimated the extent of potential production that could not be realized due to the technical
375 inefficiency of chickpea production. This was computed by region as a difference between the actual and
376 potential chickpea yields (Table 7). As presented in table 7 the average TE score was 0.5678 for Amhara,

377 0.4936 for Oromia, and 0.5236 for SNNP and the overall average TE Score for the three regions was
378 0.5314. Thus it is evident that the chickpea farms, on average, were operating only at 53.14% of their
379 potential. This suggests a scope for increasing the efficiency of production by 46.86%. That means the
380 potentiality of chickpea production can be up by almost 1.86 times (almost double) from the current level
381 if all the farms operate at their full TE. Our analysis suggests that the unrealized chickpea production due
382 to technical inefficiency, which can be considered as lost production, was highest in the Oromia region
383 (1910.10 kg ha⁻¹) followed by SNNP (1628.65 kg ha⁻¹) and Amhara (1180.41 kg ha⁻¹). Thus chickpea
384 yields can be significantly increased by increasing the technical efficiency of chickpea production by
385 encouraging the farmers to adopt improved technologies and practices.

386 **Table 7 about here**

387

388 **4. Discussion**

389 We discuss the results here in three steps. First, we discuss how the chickpea crop output is
390 influenced by the input use (land, seed, labor, fertilizer, and pesticide). Secondly, we discuss how the
391 efficiency of chickpea production is affected by environmental variables. Finally, we discuss the potential
392 for enhancing chickpea productivity and production.

393 Our analysis reveals that farmers in the three study regions (Amhara, Oromia, and SNNP) employ
394 different types and levels of technology in chickpea production. While these differences are not necessarily
395 surprising, they shed light on the ability of farmers to use improved farm technologies in chickpea
396 production. Hence, our study provides important insights about the farmers who transition from low to high
397 chickpea productivity and production levels.

398

399 The stochastic frontier analysis identified the key determinants that significantly influence the
400 efficiency of chickpea production. The size of land allocated to chickpea on the farm by a household

401 significantly impacted the chickpea production performance. Relatively larger chickpea farms performed
402 better, most likely benefiting from the specialization and economies of scale. In other words, if farmers
403 allocate suboptimal land sizes to chickpea on their farms, their production performance decreases. Thus,
404 farmers could improve chickpea production by increasing land allocation to chickpea cultivation. This is
405 similar to the findings of Jirgi et al. (2010), Assefa et al. (2020), and Hailemaraim (2015) in Ethiopia, but
406 of courses requires land to be available without trade-offs. Under the current production system, chickpea
407 specialization on relatively more land per farm would benefit farmers, at least from an economic efficiency
408 perspective.

409 NPS fertilizer application rates was another important determinant that influenced performance of
410 chickpea production. The positive and significant coefficient of the dummy variable D1 (D1=1 if NPS is
411 used and 0 otherwise) as shared in Table 4 shows that its use had a positive impact on chickpea production.
412 However, the coefficient of the variable for the actual amount of NPS used in the production was negative
413 but not significant for the regions. These findings indicate that farmers use NPS in an inappropriate way.
414 While some farmers are below the fertilizers recommendation rates for chickpea, others might be using
415 higher NPS amount than its requirement. These findings are consistent with prior studies undertaken by
416 Hassen et al. (2015), Wogayehu and Tewodros (2015), Wongnaa (2013), Abate (2019), and Birachi et al.
417 (2011). These authors argue that the context-specific increased use of compound fertilizers is likely to
418 increase chickpea yields in Ethiopia. However, the agricultural extension system need to enhance farmers'
419 awareness on balanced and efficient fertilizer use through field demonstrations and participatory training
420 programs.

421 The pesticide use was identified as the third most important input positively influencing chickpea
422 crop performance. The chickpea production performance is likely to increase by increased use of pesticides
423 to control pest and diseases especially the pod borer (*Helicoverpa armigera* Hübner). This finding is
424 consistent with the results reported by Wongnaa (2013), Assefa et al. (2020), and Jirgi et al. (2010), who
425 found that pesticides use helped attained higher efficiency of crop production. Enhancing women and men
426 farmers' awareness through participatory extension programs and improved access to low cost financial

427 resources (credit) and input markets may encourage need-based pesticide use and optimal level of fertilizer
428 use for increased chickpea productivity and production in Ethiopia.

429 The access to and use of oxen for field operations was another important factor of chickpea
430 production. In other words, oxen positively influenced chickpea production. However, the coefficient of its
431 dummy indicates that the increased use of oxen has a positive influence on chickpea production only in the
432 Amhara region. This result suggests a need for a more efficient allocation of oxen resources especially in
433 Oromia and SNNP regions. This finding thus should be interpreted in the context of past empirical studies
434 that reported the positive and significant influence of oxen power on output (Hailemariam, 2015) and Abate
435 (2019). Our results also suggest that an increased use of labor or appropriate mechanization is likely to
436 enhance chickpea productivity and production. Harvesting and threshing were the major labor requiring
437 activities having implications for the quantity and quality of grains and straw harvested.

438 Our analysis demonstrates that an increased participation of farm household's women workers in
439 chickpea production increases technical efficiency of chickpea production in the study regions. Another
440 Ethiopian study, Mussema et al., (2014) reports that women generally did better than males in lentil and
441 chickpea management activities. Since men are involved in multiple activities including off-farm/wage
442 labor, a greater participation of household's women might have been helping in the timely completion of
443 various chickpea production activities. It might have also led to a greater involvement of women in
444 decision-making regarding the crop as a result their empowerment. We found evidence that formal
445 education of farmers can play an important role in enhancing the efficiency of chickpea production.
446 Educated farmers might have been able to access information from various sources on crop production
447 technologies, inputs, prices, and market demand. This is in line with the findings of Kebede et al. (2014),
448 Ali and Khan (2014) and Alemu et al. (2018), and Dessale (2019). These studies reported that an increase
449 in human capital augments the productivity of farmers as more educated farmers were more innovative and
450 able to perceive, interpret and respond to new information and better adopt improved technologies such as
451 fertilizers, pesticides, and planting materials much faster than their less-educated counterparts. The
452 empirical evidence through this study indicates that the farmers' experience of chickpea crop production

453 might not always be an important factor influencing the efficiency of production especially when a crop is
454 cultivated by a large number of farmers in the region such as chickpea in Ethiopia. However, enabling
455 farmers' participation in technology transfer programs was identified as a key factor enhancing the
456 efficiency of chickpea production throughout the study regions. This finding not only demonstrates the role
457 of research and agricultural advisory services in improving the efficiency of chickpea production in
458 Ethiopia but also underlines the need for policy support to design appropriate participatory technology
459 development and dissemination programs to bridge the yield gaps in chickpea crop contributing to the food
460 security of the country.

461 Apart from these household-specific variables, the increased rainfall variability adversely
462 influenced the efficiency of chickpea production. The increased rainfall variability results in both
463 waterlogging of soils due to heavy rainfall events and moisture deficit during subsequent dry spells. This
464 evidence, therefore, makes a strong case for investment and capacity building for the adoption of in-situ
465 rainwater management practices such as ridge and furrow, broad bed and furrow systems, water spreading
466 weirs, ex-situ rainwater harvesting for supplemental irrigation, etc in the vulnerable areas to help mitigate
467 the impact of longer dry spells as well as water logging conditions due to climatic extremes on chickpea
468 production.

469 In our analysis, the distribution pattern of TE and chickpea yields show a positive association and
470 an upward trend (figure 4). Thus, improving technical efficiency will help farmers increase crop yield at
471 the same level of inputs or achieve the same level of yield at lesser inputs. However, some farmers were
472 obtaining high yields with lower TE, and also, few farmers were registering low yields with higher TE.
473 That might be due to excess or sub-optimal level of input use.

474
475 Globally, a growing body of empirical research on economic efficiency analysis shows that the
476 technical efficiency of agricultural production on average is about 70%. This value is far lower in many
477 developing countries (Bravo et al., 1993; Heshmati and Mulugeta, 1996; Seyoum et al. 1998; Sherlund et
478 al., 2002; Linh, 2012;). The technical efficiency analysis in this study (table 5) shows that on average,

479 chickpea farmers in Ethiopia attained only 53.14% of the maximum possible (frontier) output that the most
480 efficient farmers were able to achieve at the given level of input use and technology. It implies that the
481 farmers could increase chickpea output by about 46.86% using the same cultivars and same level of inputs
482 if they become technically efficient adopting improved production practices; conversely, they could
483 produce the present level of output with much lower level of inputs use.

484 In this study, the maximum value of TGR was 1 for all the regions, which indicates that the production
485 frontier for each of the three regions is converging with meta frontier at some points. Meta frontier
486 represents technically the most efficient points of production where a farm household produces the highest
487 level of chickpea at any given level of inputs across three regions. The result shows that some farmers in
488 all three regions were producing at their optimum level (i.e. the highest production level at given inputs)
489 vis-a-vis the meta frontier. This suggests that the available technology of chickpea production has reached
490 all the regions of Ethiopia. Nevertheless, the vast differences in technology use and technical efficiency
491 across farm households in all three study regions suggest a significant potential to enhance the technical
492 efficiency of chickpea production in Ethiopia by promoting farmer to farmer learnings within and across
493 regions.

494 Our estimates suggest that if all farmers operate at the same level of efficiency as the most efficient
495 farmers, the chickpea yields could be increased by about 90% at the current level of input use. Suppose
496 farmers overcome some of the practical limitations in accessing the knowledge-based interventions and
497 capital and adapt to biophysical constraints; in that case, it might be possible to increase the average
498 technical efficiency of chickpea production from the current level of 0.53 to 0.75 if not 1. Thus, chickpea
499 production in Ethiopia could be increased from its current level of about 500,000 t to about 750,000 t by
500 improving TE while narrowing the yield gaps.

501 **5. Conclusions and policy implications**

502 This study analyzed technical efficiencies and technology gap ratios of chickpea production in three
503 regions of Ethiopia- Amhara, Oromia and SNNP using a robust stochastic meta-frontier approach. The

504 regional TE scores, TGRs, and MTEs, were different for each of the three regions¹¹. Based on our
505 analysis, we conclude that a large proportion of farmers produce lower outputs for the level of inputs, or
506 use more inputs to get the same output level as the best performing farmers obtain in their region. Hence,
507 there is an enormous potential for increasing chickpea production in these regions by improving the
508 technical efficiency of crop production. The evidence from this study also suggests that realigning gender
509 priorities at the farm level in the conventionally male-dominated extension system would enhance the
510 efficiency of chickpea production. There is a need to, organize gender-responsive training (by changing
511 the approach, timing, and place of training) and refocus it on women to sustainably intensify chickpea
512 production. Access to labor/farm machinery and oxen are the other key drivers to improve production
513 performance. The farmers' increased access to improved seeds, fertilizers and pesticides were critically
514 important to improve chickpea productivity, however, there is a need to enhance farmers' awareness of
515 the rational use of fertilizers to have a positive effect on chickpea performance. Knowledge-based
516 interventions focused on the appropriate level and methods of applying different inputs mainly supporting
517 women farmers would be vital in harnessing the full potential of chickpea production in Ethiopia by
518 enhancing its efficiency of production. Policy support for enhanced small-scale mechanization, especially
519 for harvesting and threshing, would mitigate labour requirement and improve the performance of
520 chickpea production, reduce drudgery, and enable better utilization of crop residue as livestock fodder.
521 Supporting improved in-situ rainwater management through context specific conservation practices such
522 as ridge and furrow, water spreading weirs and broad bed and furrow systems, which help in both
523 rainwater conservation as well as drainage of excess water, will be essential to mitigate the impact of
524 increasing variability of rainfall (CV of rainfall).

¹¹ Production frontiers involved here are defined by the model and within the sample values. This implies that there may be techniques of production, not practiced by any of the farmers in the sample, which could yield a much higher output for the same level of input.

525 Harnessing the potential of chickpea production through enhancing efficiencies would contribute
526 to enhanced food security, reduce income poverty and increase foreign exchange through exports. A
527 targeted chickpea production intensification strategy would align well with Ethiopia’s Agricultural
528 Development Led Industrialization (ADLI) strategy, and Growth and Transformation Plan-II which focuses
529 on high-value crops, livestock, and market orientation. Enhancing the efficiency of chickpea production is
530 achievable to a large extent through improving farmers' access to improved seed, need-based and gender-
531 responsive extension support, and farmers’ participation in technology development programs.

532 A large proportion of farmers do not have the required skills and awareness to use various inputs
533 and technologies optimally. A country or region close to the meta frontier might have to make additional
534 investments in research to develop new technologies, strengthen the agricultural extension system and
535 promote enabling policies providing incentives for disseminating the available technologies to distant
536 areas and low-efficiency farmers. The availability of highly efficient farmers in each region suggests that
537 promoting ‘farmer to farmer’ extension is likely to significantly increase the efficiency of chickpea
538 production and prevent losses due to yield gaps in Ethiopia.

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547 **Conflict of interest**

548 The authors declare no competing interest.

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755 Figure 3: Conceptual framework for meta-frontier model

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a: Difference between individual farm and group frontier production efficiency;
 b: Difference between group's frontier and meta frontier, and
 c: Individual farm's production efficiency

775 Figure 4: Distribution of technical efficiency (TE) and technical gap ratio (TGR) in three chickpea-
 776 growing areas of Ethiopia

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779 **Table 1: Proportion of area under Kabuli and Desi chickpea, by varieties and regions (%)**

Regions	Kabuli cultivars (% area)				Total Kabuli	Desi cultivars (% area)			Local Desi	Total Desi	Total chick pea area (%)
	Shasho	Ejere	Habru	Arerti		Mariye	Dubie	Natoli			
	ICCV- 93512	FLIP 97-263c	FLIP 88-42c	FLIP 89- 84c		K-850- 3/27xF37 8	PGRC	ICCX- 910112-6			
Amhara	0.58	0	11.68	41.96	54.22	0.58	5.79	0.48	38.93	45.78	100
Oromia	4.62	1	7.82	63.42	76.86	0.74	0.19	0.85	21.36	23.14	100
SNPP	0	4.11	18.63	29.04	51.78	0	1.64	1.37	45.21	48.22	100
Overall	2.68	1.04	10.45	51.9	66.07	0.6	2.28	0.78	30.27	33.93	100

780 Source: Authors' estimates using farm household level primary data

Table2: Basic statistics at the farm household level of the variables used in the study

Variable	Amhara				Oromia				SNNP				Overall			
	Max	Min	Mean	SD	Max	Min	Mean	SD	Max	Min	Mean	SD	Max	Min	Mean	SD
Chickpea production (kg)	5000.00	60.00	608.13	475.72	10300.00	57.50	1354.20	1367.29	3400.00	50.00	583.83	579.79	10300.00	50.00	903.54	1017.62
Land use (kert)	8.00	0.13	1.62	1.12	13.00	0.25	2.88	2.18	7.00	0.25	1.59	1.37	13.00	0.13	2.12	1.77
Seed use (kg)	200.00	5.50	41.22	29.20	500.00	2.00	102.10	85.49	140.00	1.00	32.80	28.35	500.00	1.00	64.35	66.24
Labor use (days)	304.00	4.63	39.36	30.53	351.00	5.00	73.15	66.57	160.00	8.00	43.31	32.09	351.00	4.63	53.50	51.03
NPS use (kg)	125.00	0.00	5.70	13.37	200.00	0.00	8.00	25.33	75.00	0.00	12.45	16.45	200.00	0.00	7.64	19.56
Pesticide use (liter)	12.00	0.00	0.69	1.00	12.00	0.00	1.16	1.39	4.00	0.00	0.59	0.81	12.00	0.00	0.86	1.17
Oxen for ploughing (number)	8.00	0.00	1.90	1.01	12.00	0.00	3.07	2.07	6.00	0.00	1.97	1.20	12.00	0.00	2.38	1.65
Exp. of growing chickpea (year)	55.00	1.00	20.65	10.57	60.00	0.00	16.51	10.91	44.00	1.00	12.59	9.37	60.00	0.00	17.77	10.91
Proportion of woman in household workforce	0.86	0.00	0.45	0.16	0.80	0.00	0.42	0.17	0.80	0.17	0.47	0.16	0.86	0.00	0.44	0.16
Household average age (year)	68.67	20.00	33.01	6.69	63.00	18.50	33.93	7.12	60.00	22.50	33.50	7.58	68.67	18.50	33.45	7.00
Household average education (year)	10.50	0.00	3.52	2.07	10.40	0.00	4.31	1.96	10.67	1.86	5.32	1.78	10.67	0.00	4.11	2.08
Participation in tech transfer program	1.00	0.00	0.16	0.36	1.00	0.00	0.37	0.48	1.00	0.00	0.50	0.50	1.00	0.00	0.29	0.46
Proportion of chickpea area under improved varieties	1.00	0.00	0.547	0.452	1.00	0.00	0.743	0.446	1.00	0.00	0.616	0.448	1.00	0.00	0.636	0.451
CV of Rainfall	33.45	19.34	23.35	4.52	23.77	16.27	18.01	2.05	20.38	16.23	17.88	2.04	33.45	16.23	20.38	4.31
Distance from market (km)	90.00	0.00	7.60	6.78	120.00	0.00	10.12	14.94	50.00	0.00	8.75	7.24	120.00	0.00	8.78	10.91

Note: 4 kert = 1 ha; NPS - A compound fertilizer containing nitrogen, phosphorous and Sulphur; CV – Coefficient of variation

Source: Authors' estimates using farm household level primary data

Table 3: Chickpea crop yields (kg/ha) across three regions of Ethiopia

Region	Observation	Max	Min	Mean	SD
Amhara	305	4200.00	685.71	1502.17	703.02
Oromia	273	4000.00	640.00	1879.26	854.96
SNNP	103	3680.00	680.00	1471.19	552.26
Overall	681	4200.00	626.67	1704.11	764.88

Source: Authors' estimates using farm household level primary data

Table 4: Stochastic frontier estimates for chickpea Production in three regions of Ethiopia

Variables	Amhara	Oromia	SNPP	Pooled Data	Meta Frontier
Constant_ Input	5.7624*** (0.2612)	5.6276*** (0.2430)	5.2106*** (0.1843)	5.2543*** (0.1977)	5.8691*** (0.0483)
Land use	0.6073*** (0.0560)	0.4656*** (0.0752)	0.6275*** (0.0647)	0.6155*** (0.0411)	0.5452*** (0.0134)
Seed use	0.0831* (0.0450)	0.1668*** (0.0499)	0.0115 (0.0280)	0.0984*** (0.0252)	0.1104*** (0.0083)
Labor use	0.0778* (0.0429)	0.1801*** (0.0522)	0.2919*** (0.0661)	0.1457*** (0.0361)	0.1759*** (0.0117)
NPS use	-0.0271 (0.0449)	-0.0603 (0.0572)	-0.0044 (0.0440)	-0.0307 (0.0303)	-0.0315*** (0.0115)
Pesticide use	0.0579** (0.0245)	0.1037*** (0.0334)	0.0835** (0.0381)	0.0772*** (0.0192)	0.0982*** (0.0079)
Oxen	0.1196** (0.0494)	0.1043* (0.0607)	0.1791*** (0.0477)	0.0772*** (0.0344)	0.1850*** (0.0142)
D1 (dummy NPS use)	0.3833*** (0.1106)	0.2990 (0.2073)	-0.0416 (0.1376)	0.2018** (0.0948)	0.1905*** (0.0339)
D2 (dummy pesticide use)	0.0832** (0.0408)	0.1776** (0.0825)	0.2894*** (0.0572)	0.2018*** (0.0373)	0.1931*** (0.0170)
D3 (dummy oxen use)	0.1200* (0.0684)	-0.0806 (0.0991)	0.1003 (0.1084)	-0.0763 (0.0373)	-0.1349*** (0.0170)
Constant_ Env. variable	1.1634*** (0.1550)	1.4888*** (0.1828)	1.3844*** (0.1236)	0.7510*** (0.0545)	-0.3389*** (0.1014)
Exp. of Growing Chickpea	0.0016 (0.0021)	0.0068*** (0.0027)	-0.0069** (0.0032)	-0.0002 (0.0013)	XX
Proportion of women in household workforce	-0.3170*** (0.1251)	-0.2878** (0.1462)	-0.2987** (0.1383)	-0.3831*** (0.0945)	XX
Household average Age	-0.0100*** (0.0038)	-0.0075* (0.0040)	-0.0060* (0.0032)	-0.0057*** (0.0022)	XX
Household average education	-0.0178* (0.0098)	-0.0419*** (0.0155)	-0.0322** (0.0136)	-0.0070 (0.0022)	XX
Participation in tech transfer program	-0.1002* (0.0531)	-0.2475*** (0.0663)	-0.2589*** (0.0581)	-0.0070*** (0.0358)	XX
Proportion of chickpea area under improved varieties	-0.1011** (0.0419)	-0.2747*** (0.0740)	0.0464 (0.0496)	-0.1285*** (0.0331)	XX
CV of rainfall	XX	XX	XX	XX	0.0243*** (0.0035)
Distance from market	XX	XX	XX	XX	-0.0011 (0.0013)
$\sigma_s^2 = \sigma_v^2 + \sigma_u^2$	0.0878*** (0.0135)	0.1478*** (0.0207)	0.0454*** (0.0063)	0.1125*** (0.0064)	0.0458*** (0.0070)
$\gamma = \frac{\sigma_u^2}{\sigma_s^2}$	0.8083*** (0.1719)	1.0000*** (0.0000)	1.0000*** (0.2310)	0.0000 (0.0004)	0.9658*** (0.0114)
Log likelihood	48.1719	-91.0660	15.3412	227.3181	328.8742
N	305	273	103	681	681

***, **, and * denote significance at 1, 5, and 10 % levels respectively

Source: Authors' estimates using farm household level primary data

Table 5: Summarized statistics of the different efficiency measures

Measurement	Region	Max	Min	Mean	SD
TE	Amhara	0.9510	0.2974	0.5678	0.1404
	Oromia	0.9999	0.1544	0.4936	0.1918
	SNNP	0.9856	0.2072	0.5236	0.1619
	Overall	0.9999	0.1544	0.5314	0.1692
TGR	Amhara	1.0000	0.8558	0.9711	0.0255
	Oromia	1.0000	0.8874	0.9630	0.0239
	SNNP	1.0000	0.8672	0.9622	0.0261
	Overall	1.0000	0.8558	0.9665	0.0253
MTE	Amhara	0.9949	0.1541	0.5091	0.1776
	Oromia	0.8650	0.1738	0.5069	0.1463
	SNNP	0.9197	0.2185	0.5415	0.1623
	Overall	0.9949	0.1541	0.5131	0.1636

Source: Authors' estimate using farm household level primary data

Note: TE - Technical Efficiency; TGR - Technology Gap Ratio; and MTE - Meta Technical Efficiency

Table 6: Paired t-test for various efficiency measurements across three chickpea-growing regions of Ethiopia.

	Amhara vs Oromia	Amhara vs SNNP	Oromia vs SNNP
Group TE	5.2544***	2.4744**	-1.5197
TGR	3.9442***	3.0088***	0.27032
MTE	0.16052	-1.712**	-1.8931*

***, **, and * denote significance at the 1, 5, and 10 % levels respectively

Source: Authors' estimate using farm household level primary data

Table 7: Actual and potential yield obtained through improved technical efficiency (TE) for chickpea crop for the three regions of Ethiopia

Particulars	Maximum	Minimum	Average	SD
Amhara				
Actual yield(kg/ha)	4200.00	685.71	1502.17	703.02
TE estimate	0.9510	0.2974	0.5678	0.1404
Potential yield (kg/ha)	5319.59	1499.55	2802.81	732.64
Potential production loss (kg/ha)	2993.65	216.62	1180.41	439.81
Oromia				
Actual yield(kg/ha)	4000.00	640.00	1879.26	854.96
TE estimate	0.9999	0.1544	0.4936	0.1918
Potential yield (kg/ha)	6763.57	2042.73	3798.53	773.25
Potential production loss (kg/ha)	5039.68	0.40	1910.10	833.85
SNNP				
Actual yield(kg/ha)	3680.00	680.00	1471.19	552.26
TE estimate	0.9856	0.2072	0.5236	0.1619
Potential yield (kg/ha)	9345.49	811.69	3085.38	1522.52
Potential production loss (kg/ha)	6145.49	11.69	1628.65	1132.78
Overall				
Actual yield(kg/ha)	4200.00	626.67	1704.11	764.88
TE estimate	0.9999	0.1544	0.5314	0.1692
Potential yield (kg/ha)	9345.49	811.69	3244.72	1020.49
Potential production loss (kg/ha)	6145.49	0.40	1540.73	819.30

Source: Authors' estimate using farm household level primary data